

ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH ON THE ECONOMIC HISTORY OF THE TURKESTAN ASSR (1991-2020)

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Abstract

In the years of independence in this article Historical research on the economic history of the Turkestan ASSR, which played an important role in the history of statehood of Uzbekistan, is analyzed. In addition, the research analyzes from a historical point of view the research conducted during the years of independence on issues such as military communism, food intelligence and the new economic policy of the Soviet government in the country.

Development of history has reached a new level on the basis of radical changes taking place since the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan . In recent years, special attention has been paid to the study of the history of national statehood on the basis of new approaches, based on primary sources. Therefore, it is important to conduct research on the history of statehood of the Uzbek people on the basis of an objective approach, to prevent the falsification of the past.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev noted, "Social sciences and humanities play an important role in the development of our national spirituality, its integration into the lives of our people, especially our youth.

One truth we all need to understand deeply: we need to create a national history with a national spirit. Otherwise, it will not have an educational effect. We need to teach our youth to learn from history, to draw conclusions, to equip them with the science of history, historical thinking. For this, first of all, I think it is time to develop a concept for the development of history in Uzbekistan until 2030 ... "[1]

Indeed, the Turkestan ASSR is a very complex and controversial period in the history of Uzbek statehood. During the years of independence, many historical studies on the history of the Turkestan ASSR were conducted on the basis of the concept of independence. Among them is a study of the economic history of the republic. The study of historical research on the economic history of the Turkestan ASSR from the point of view of historiography is important in attracting researchers to unexplored topics in the economic history of the republic, as well as in revealing the historiographical nature of the economic policy of the Soviet government. Soviet government wide coverage surround take , For almost 14 years, the Economic Councils -have been subordinating the

economy of not only the entire Soviet state, but also its constituent Turkestan ASSR, BXSr, XXSR, then the Uzbek SSR, the Turkmen SSR and other autonomous republics and autonomous regions to the interests of the Center. holding firmly in his hand[2] , it can be seen that it has paved the way on a large scale.

The development of history has entered a new stage on the basis of radical reforms in Uzbekistan. During this period, special attention is paid to the study of the history of national statehood on the basis of new approaches, based on historical sources. The period of the Turkestan ASSR, which covers the history of Uzbek statehood from 1917 to 1924, was also conducted on the basis of an objective and truthful approach, as the years of independence provided access to a number of archival documents and many other sources .

In particular, some aspects of the socio-cultural life of the Turkestan ASSR: armed movements against the Soviets, regulators, the government's religious policy. However, no special research work on the historiography of economic issues of the Turkestan ASSR has been created. Nevertheless, information on the subject can be found in studies on the history of the Turkestan ASSR. This kind of research works in the Soviet era, M.Nazarov [3] singari scientists by take visited _ Independence years esa Turkiston Of the ASSR economic some of his life fronts dedicated to scientific research works Many scientific researches were carried out by I.Haydarov [4], A.Abdullaev [5], K.Rajabov, M.Haydarov, [6] Sh.Choriev[7].

Research in Q.Rajabov and Co -authored by M.Haydarov created " Turkistan History " in Turkestan _ famine , raw materials transport departure , cotton monopoly , g alla in Turkestan monopoly and food dictatorship economics of current ethyl work mu a mmolar illuminate b melted.[8]

To the economic history of Turkestan ASSR Another important study in 2018 is Sh.Choriev by In his dissertation, the researcher tried to reveal the source significance of many archival documents on the economic history of the Turkestan ASSR[9]. In addition, the study focuses on economic problems in Turkestan, famine, the "card" system, the food directorate, the new economic policy in the field of archival sources. also revealed its importance. It has also incorporated many economic statistics into scientific consumption.

Doctoral dissertation "Consequences of the policy of centralization of the Soviet government in Turkestan (1917-1924)"[10] also plays an important role in the research. The study focuses on the negative and positive results of the Soviet government's policy of centralization in the management of the national economy of Turkestan, as well as the economic situation in the country. In addition, after the October coup, important historical issues such as famine and its

consequences, the activities of economic organizations, cotton monopoly were revealed.

Another important study of the history of economic life of the Turkestan ASSR during the years of independence is the dissertation of H. Kulliev "The emergence of the economic and spiritual foundations of the dictatorial regime in Turkestan." In his research, the author describes the introduction of "military communism" in Turkestan by the Soviet government, the mass nationalization of production, the resulting reduction in arable land and a number of industrial enterprises, the transition to cotton monopoly and the tragic consequences of these economic reforms.[11]

The three-volume book "History of Uzbekistan", published during the years of independence, also describes the "military communism", socialism, grain monopoly, food distribution, famine of 1917-1923, the economic crisis and the crisis in the Turkestan ASSR after the October Revolution. In order to regulate the economic life of the country, the Center provided general information on the implementation of the New Economic Policy since 1921.[12]

Among the scientific researches devoted to the economic life of the Turkestan ASSR is a research work by S. Hoshimov entitled "From the history of the autonomous representations of the Turkestan ASSR and the Uzbek SSR in Moscow (1918-1991)." The difference between this research and the above-mentioned research is that the researcher provided information about the Autonomous Representation of the Turkestan ASSR in Moscow, its activities, the role of the representative office in economic processes and the work done during the economic crisis in the country. According to the study, this authority also acted on the instructions of the center. [13]

In his dissertation "Problems and changes in approaches to the study of the history of the Turkestan ASSR in Uzbek historiography (1918-2020)" researcher G.Abdulkhay noted that in 1918 the Bolshevik government proposed Soviet-type autonomy in order to prevent the escalation of national conflicts in the country. The existence of copies of all-Russian documents justified the division of the population into "rich and poor" under the mechanism of "class management" of the state. The researcher also notes that the Soviet literature assessed the Bolsheviks as "political freedom", "brotherly international aid", "selfless and wise policy of the Communist Party", but in fact it was a dictatorship.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the above brief analysis differs from previous research on the subject in recent years. It includes both sources from the period, relevant archival

documents and official reports, as well as foreign studies covering the economic life of the Turkestan ASSR and periodicals. was written as a result of studying the data. For this reason, it can be much more effective to learn about the economic life of the country from scientific works created during the years of independence. It should be noted that during the years of independence, as a result of research on the economic life of the Turkestan ASSR, a number of scientific studies were created on the basis of the concept of an objective approach, free from Soviet ideology. However, Uzbek historians still face the banking sector, water taxes, land allocation and other unresolved issues. For this reason, the Turkestan ASSR is working hard to create a comprehensive scientific literature and historical analysis of the economic sphere of the USSR. In creating such a study, the researcher is required to study the literature of the Soviet era, foreign studies, relevant archival documents and conduct research on the basis of an objective approach without deviating from any ideology and ideas.

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